

Some Unknown Monument in Nuh, Haryana

Dr. Banani Bhattacharyya

Deputy Director, Department of Archaeology & Museums, Haryana

Accepted: 18 November 2021 / Published online: 26 December 2021

Introduction

Nuh, a district of Haryana bounded by Gurgaon district on the north, Rewari district on the west and Faridabad and Palwal districts on the east. Physiographically, this district can be broadly divided into two tracts-upland and lowland. Nuh-Punahana plain spread over parts of Nuh tehsil and area between Alwar and Ajabgarh rock formation and eastern part of Ferozpur Jhirka tehsil. The region is agriculturally poor. Ferozpur Jhirka uplands cover the central and southern part of Ferozpur Jhirka Tehsil. The ridges and uplands are dissected by rainfed streams from both sides.

The district is predominantly populated by the Meos, who are agriculturalists, and Muslims. It is known for its rich cultural heritage and historical background. The Meos, who trace their roots to the early Aryan invasion of northern India, known as Kshatriyas, have preserved the social and the cultural identity of this area. 13th-16th century CE: During the Pre-Mughal period, the area was under the slave dynasty of Aibak though it could never be completely conquered due to intermittent resistance and fights by local Meos. Bahadur Nahar, known as the founder of Khanzada dynasty of Mewat, rose as the strongest Mewati ruler in this period. Gurgaon and Mewat came under the direct control of Lodhi dynasty after Bahlol Lodhi's conquest in 1451. However, the Khanzadas of Mewat were not totally suppressed during this period. It remained part of the Empire under the Sur dynasty. 16th-18th century CE: during Akbar's reign, the district was a part of the Subah of Delhi. With the decline of the Mughal Empire, it was segregated and distributed among the neighboring chiefs of Farrukhnagar, Ghasera and Jat rulers of Bharatpur. 19th-20th century CE: In 1803, Gurgaon district was passed into the hands of the British after Lord Lake's conquest.

SARAI LASKARABAD -

A small detour from the main road between Naurangpur and Tauru road leads to a nondescript village called Sarai, which derives its name from a Mughal-era rest-house or sarai; its antiquity can be traced back through an inscription on the gateway.

The institution of sarai was an important feature of the Indian society of medieval period. Sarais were generally large enclosure providing board stable fodder, entertainment and similar other facilities to the travelers. These were located in large towns and on important routes at reasonable distances in the country-side. All the available evidence about the sarais in India pertains to the period following the Turkish conquest, which might indicate that this institution in its form that is familiar to us through historical evidence was introduced in this country by the Turks. There is definite evidence to show that the construction of sarais as a public welfare measure by state during the Mughal period was not a new phenomenon. Travel in medieval India was undertaken largely by traders, merchants, pilgrims and state-officials and their troopers. It may be presumed that with the intensification of economy and resulting expansion of commerce during the 16th and 17th centuries, the movement of trade would become more brisk. The increasing frequency of travel would naturally create greater demand for a larger number of sarais as well as better facilities in them. Ample evidences are available in the form of general statements appearing in the Persian chronicles as well as in the accounts of the European travelers to the effect that Mughal India had a very large number of sarais well placed along the main routes.

As the Delhi-Gurgaon Expressway cuts through Naurangpur, some 20 kilometres from the heart of Gurugram, one lands at a maze of under-construction buildings that are fast sprouting across the skyline of South Haryana. Products of rampant construction, these buildings punctuate the

roads on both sides — some frozen with partially completed structures, some waiting to be sold, and others with their absentee flat owners. Cranes dangle in the air even as dust bellows from the mounds of construction material dumped on the ground floors of these buildings. Skirting the northern foothills of the Aravalli mountain range, these buildings make way for the sun-kissed mustard fields as one heads toward Tauru in Nuh (erstwhile Mewat).

This old Sarai is situated in the village which was basically a resting house or halting shelter for the travelers and the military troops as well. There is an inscription on its gateway which describes year of construction of this sarai in 1000 Hizri i.e. 1592 AD. It was constructed by some Khan Feroz during the time of Mughal Emperor Akbar and was named as Sarai Laskarabad, which indicates its purpose of construction for shelters to moving Laskars (Military convoy in Persian). The sarai building has a high walled enclosure built of stone masonry. The wall is constructed of stone, un-plastered while the interiors are plastered. A major crack is visible on the main entrance including several other minor cracks. The structure appears like a fortress. It has octagonal shaped pillared towers on its corners. Its entering gateway has cabins for watchman and all along its inner side of enclosing walls is a continuous row of arched masonry shelters. The roof of that row of arched rooms acts as a path along the inner side of rampart for the watch and word purposes. A small mosque was built close to its entrance.

The landscape changes and animal herders can be seen leading their cattle into the fields that flank both sides of the road from Naurangpur to Tauru road. The trail is largely innocuous and is unlikely to attract any spectacular attention. However, it's from here that a small detour off the main road leads one to a nondescript village called Sarai — which is imbued in history but whose past has largely been forgotten.

TOMB AT GUMAT BIHARI

An abandoned huge medieval tomb (14th-15th Century AD) is located in Gumat Bihari village in Nagina, Nuh. The tomb is built on a square plan, a popular style of Pathan architecture. The tomb is unique in style having a huge arched basement as platform for the upper structure. It has also turrets along the circumference of high bulbous dome with a lotus finial resting on an octagonal drum-base. The exterior of the tomb is decorated and detailed in brickwork, with niches above door level along with arched doorways and parapet.

General View of the Tomb

Inside the Tomb - Ceiling

Today this huge structure is lying in disrepair. It is crumbling with plaster peeling off especially in base level and roofs leaking. It is presently laying closed in utter neglect. However, this grand monument is still apparently intact. The monuments can be renovated and developed as a part of heritage attraction in the district.

FORT OF KOTLA HILL

Kotla, seven miles south-west of Nuh in district Mewat, was once the capital of the *khanzada* chief Bahadur Nahar Khan. It is now only a small village of a few houses. Kotla village is

surrounded by hillocks on its three sides. On the top of the western hillocks this fort is located which is constructed by Bahadur Nahar Khan Mewati, the Mewat Chief. The fort, located in Kotla Hill -10 km South of Nuh town, had been used as the headquarter of Mewat Chief. The location of this fort is in between valleys and peaks of hillocks which is difficult for anyone to reach there. The walls of the fort are built with stone boulders. The wide ditch dug for defense purpose is now functioning as a Nala to drain out the rain water from surrounding area . On an inscription over the ruined gateway, the date of its construction was written as 1392-1400 AD. The name ‘Kotla’ signifies as ‘fort on the hill’. Cunningham assumed that the site was probably chosen for its strategic importance, as it is protected on the east by the large lake named *Dahar*, which is 4 to 5 miles in length by upwards and 2 miles in breadth.(A Cunningham, *ASI Report 1882-83*, XX, 129-133.)

General View of the Fort

Another View of the Fort

BAHADUR NAHAR KHAN'S MOSQUE, KOTLA

The Mosque is 6.5 kilometres from Nuh city in the *Kotla village*. The red sandstone and Grey quartzite tomb has inscription on the ruined gateway, dating it to 1392-1400 CE. The mosque is a square structure on raised platform. The surface of the exterior is simple. The interior is curved with red sandstone and the openings with jaalis. Remain of an old well also visible near the mosque. This mosque is situated on a high mound in the middle of the village. It is built with stones blocks. It is the great *mosque*, contemporary of Timur. There was a long inscription on the gateway, which gives the date of construction of the mosque. But at present, there is neither gateway nor any inscription found on this place. The inscription reads very much like a passage from the memoirs of Firoz Shah, which were written only a few years before his death. From the extract of the inscription it appears that this much lauded king was an intolerant bigot, who persecuted his Hindu subjects on account of their religion.

The construction of the *mosque* was begun in the reign of Muhammad Shah, son of Firoz Tughlaq, when, he (Muhammad Shah) occupied Kotla during his campaign against the *Mewatis* in A.H. 795. Muhammad shah having died in A.H. 796, the building was not finished until A.H. 803.

The *mosque* stands at the western end of grand courtyard, measuring 92 feet in length to the inner side. It is approached by a grand flight of twenty steps and then four steps to reach the courtyard. The flight of steps is 15 feet high. The mosque is 66' long and 35' broad outside and

59'.5" by 29'.5" inside. Basically the breadth being just half the length. It consists of three aisles with seven arched opening to the front, making twenty one spans, of which only the middle one is covered by a very small dome, all the rest having flat roofs. There are *mihirabs* in each span of the back wall. To the right side of the central *mihrab* a six steps *mimbar* is decorated. Three openings in each end wall are closed by stout lattices of red stone.

This structure is made of square quartzite blocks. At present three doorways of this mosque are closed with wooden door structures. In the southern side, there is a narrow flight of steps leading to the terrace. The stairs were repaired by the local people but red bricks were used in place of the quartzite blocks. The outer corners of the backside have been strengthened by small sloping minars, similar to those of Firoz Shah's period. The pillars in the south-west corner of the courtyard of the mosque are standing near *vazu* taps in decorative manners. It seems that these pillars are the ancient pillars; it may be re-used material from the ancient Indian temples. It is same as used in the Firoz Shah's time. According to Rodgers the architecture of the interior resembles the Hindu style. The courtyard is bounded on each side by a thick massive wall. The whole of the south wall had fallen down but now it has been restored by the local people. The red sand stone pillars are lying down in the courtyard in a neglected condition. It may be the pillars of the tomb of Bahadur Nahar Khan.

General View of the Mosque

Steps of the Mosque

CHHATRIS AND KUAN AT MEOLI

Meoli village is located 7 km away from sub-district headquarter Nuh and 7km away from district headquarter Mewat at Nuh. The ancestral villages of the Deharwal Meos were at Meoli which was colonized by Mewa Singh. Jagga records inform that Mewa Singh was the head of fifty-two Khorei (settlements) in the Kala Pahad. The term Dehrawal was derived from Dehar which comprised of the low lying area near the Kotla lake in the Nuh region. Meoli, a fairly old village has the remains of a pair of Chhatris side by side and a Kuan which were built in an architectural style of the medieval era. The construction material used, selection of its location and the style adopted for its superstructure obviously were depended on the nature of the soil and terrain, the amount of average rainfall, purpose and availability of masonry expertise. Main purpose was to lift required water. While architecture of chhatris are as usual but the well is cylindrical in shape through its depth and diameter.

General view of the Chhatra and Kuan

Bibliography:

- Asher, Catherine B. *The New Cambridge History of India: Architecture of Mughal India*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2003
- Brown, Percy. *Indian Architecture: Islamic Period*. Bombay: D B Taraporevala Sons & Co., 1997.
- Cunningham, A., *ASI Report 1882-83*, XX, 129-133.
- Desai, Z. A. *Indo-Islamic Architecture*. Delhi: Publication Division, Government of India, 1970
- Elliot, and Dowson, ed., *Futuh-i-Firoz Shahi, History of India as told by its own Historians*, III, (repr. Allahabad, 1964) 380
- Grover, Satish. *Islamic Architecture in India*. New Delhi: Galgotia Publishing Company, 1996.
- Gulia, Yaspal. *Heritage of Haryana*, New Delhi, 1912
- Nath, R., *Studies in Medieval Indian Architecture*, New Delhi: M.D. Publications Pvt. Ltd., 1995